

Reduced recombination through the CZTS/CdS interface engineering in monograin layer solar cells

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Abstract

The power conversion efficiency of CZTS solar cells is still limited by deep defects, low minority carrier lifetime and high recombination rates at the CZTS/CdS interface. The objective of this study was to find an effective method to reduce interface recombination of CZTS monograin layer solar cells. Two-step heterojunction formation process was applied by controlling the intermixing of Cd and Cu in the CZTS/CdS interface, which resulted in improved device efficiency up to 11.7%. Surface analysis by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy confirmed the Cd diffusion into surface of CZTS after CdS air-annealing by forming an ultra-thin $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}_x\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{SnS}_4$ layer. Also, external quantum efficiency measurements showed that the absorption edge shifts to longer wavelengths with addition of Cd into CZTS surface layer. This surface modification and replacement of CdS:Cu buffer layer by fresh CdS greatly reduced the interface recombination and improved the junction quality, contributing to an enhancement of $J_{\text{SC}} \sim 3 \text{ mA/cm}^2$ (from 20.5 to 23.6 mA/cm^2), and fill factor $\sim 14\%$ (from 59.4 to 67.7%). Serial resistance of the CZTS monograin layer solar cells was significantly reduced from $2.4 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ to $0.67 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$. To understand in more detail the electrical behavior of highest efficiency CZTS monograin layer solar cell, the temperature dependent current–voltage characteristics were analyzed.

1 Introduction

Photovoltaic (PV) technology can provide a significant fraction of the world's energy demands if solar devices are composed of earth-abundant and nontoxic materials. Among the inorganic absorber materials, kesterite materials ($\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S},\text{Se})_4$) are promising candidates because they combine near optimum direct bandgap, high optical absorption coefficient of $\sim 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the visible light region, with predicted theoretical power conversion efficiency (PCE) more than 30%, and constituent elements are earth-abundant, cheap, and non-toxic. The major issue for kesterite is a low open circuit voltage (V_{OC}) due to low minority carrier lifetime [1] and high recombination rates at the heterojunction interface, as well as in the bulk. The highest recorded efficiency for $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$ (CZTS) based solar cell has been reported to be 11% [2]. The highest V_{OC} of 809 mV is demonstrated for ordered CZTS [3]. Regardless of these achievements, the V_{OC} deficit is still large compared to $\text{Cu}(\text{In},\text{Ga})\text{Se}_2$ (CIGS) based solar cells and therefore, significant research is still needed in this field. Several groups have shown improvements of PCE with elemental intermixing at the absorber/buffer interface by post-annealing process [2,4]. Su *et al.*[5] reported that by post-annealing complete Cd-alloyed pure sulfide device,

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3 which includes ITO as window layer, showed efficiency of 12.6%. Our group's latest study [6] showed
4 that soft air-annealing of CZTS/CdS at 175-200 °C improved device performance mainly due to
5 decreased series resistance (R_s) value, but annealing at higher temperature degraded the devices due to
6 the formation of Cu-rich CZTS absorber surface close to the CZTS/CdS interface. Analysis results
7 showed that our CZTS monograin layer solar cells have several recombination routes. Unfortunately,
8 none of these routes disappeared with air annealing of the CZTS/CdS interface. Therefore, the post-
9 annealing of CZTS/CdS is not the definite solution for reducing interface recombination and solve the
10 V_{OC} -deficit. It must be also considered that with post-annealing of CZTS/CdS, the diffusion of Cu from
11 absorber to buffer layer is possible, which increases the photoconductivity of CdS and increases the R_s
12 of devices [7,8]. Other option to reduce the recombination and boost the V_{OC} is Cd ion soaking
13 treatment, which is also used in CIGS technologies [9–11]. Results have shown that Cd ion soaking
14 process facilitates the Cd diffusion into CZTS surface [10,12], increases the minority carrier lifetime
15 and reduces the non-radiative recombination [10], and decreases the R_s of the CZTS devices [9].

24 An enhancement in the performance of CZTS monograin layer solar cells has been achieved in several
25 ways. For example, an addition of low concentration of Ag (1% from Cu) into $Cu_2(Cd,Zn)SnS_4$ lattice
26 led to the increased V_{OC} values of the devices and improved the efficiency from 6.6% to 8.7% due to
27 the reduction of the non-radiative recombination and/or interface recombination, but the V_{OC} deficit
28 remained unsolved [13]. The influence of order-disorder in CZTS monograin powders was investigated
29 in the study [14]. Results showed that the low-temperature thermal treatments increased the degree of
30 Cu-Zn ordering and devices showed increased V_{OC} values up to 784 mV and CZTS monograin layer
31 solar cell efficiency of 9.1%. Nevertheless, the V_{OC} deficit still remained large compared to
32 corresponding bandgap values (E_g). PL study showed that reduced Cu-Zn disordering of the crystals
33 lead to increased bandgap energy by about 100 meV and change in recombination type from band to
34 tail to band to impurity type. The latter involves the deep trap (~ 200 meV) related recombination and
35 reduces the positive effect of the band gap increase to the V_{OC} in the least disordered material. Also, the
36 performance of CZTS monograin layer solar cells was effectively improved up to 9.4% by using
37 oxidative chemical treatment before the formation of the heterojunction [15]. The effect was attributed
38 to the formation of passivation layer of SnO_2 on CZTS surface. Although, all our previous developments
39 have shown good progress, the main issues have been remained.

50 In this study, we applied two-step process in the heterojunction formation to reduce the interface
51 recombination and improve the junction quality, and the current–voltage (I - V) measurements showed
52 device efficiency up to 11.7%. Serial resistance of the CZTS monograin layer solar cells was
53 significantly reduced from $2.4 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ [6] to $0.67 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$. In this work, we analyze the influence of the
54 Cd diffusion into surface of CZTS and replacement of Cu doped CdS by fresh CdS buffer layer on the
55 electrical behavior of highest efficiency CZTS monograin layer solar cell by temperature dependent I -
56 V characteristics.

2 Experimental.

In this work, $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$ monograin powder was synthesized from binary compounds- CuS, ZnS and SnS with purity of 99.999% in the liquid phase of potassium iodide (KI) flux material in sealed quartz ampoule at 740 °C. The composition of monograins was analyzed by energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). The bulk of crystals had average composition ratios of $\text{Cu}/(\text{Zn}+\text{Sn}) = 0.91$ and $\text{Zn}/\text{Sn} = 1.08$. Standard post-growth processes being in use in our lab were applied. Post-growth chemical etching was done with 1 vol% Br in methanol for 5 min followed by 10 wt% KCN aqueous solution for 5 min at room temperature. After the etching process, the CZTS powder was heat-treated in sealed ampoule in a dual temperature zone furnace at 840 °C in sulphur vapour ($p_s = 2050$ Torr) for 60 minutes.

The highest efficiency CZTS monograin layer solar cell (hereafter named as CZTS-modified) was prepared by using two-step process (scheme of the combined 2-step process in Figure 1 for formation of heterojunction between the CZTS and CdS. In the first step, CdS was deposited by chemical bath deposition process on powder crystals followed by annealing in air at 225 °C for 10 minutes [6]. With this step, Cd diffusion into surface of CZTS, forming an ultra-thin $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}_x\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{SnS}_4$ layer with decreased band gap at very top of absorber, is expected. At the same time, the Cu out-diffusion into the surface of CZTS and also into the buffer layer is possible and this could change the properties of the buffer layer. Therefore, after annealing step, CdS was removed by concentrated HCl and fresh CdS buffer layer without additional post-annealing was deposited on the CZTS crystals. CZTS monograin layer solar cell with single step CdS buffer layer deposition followed by air annealing at 225 °C for 10 minutes was considered as a reference device in this study (hereafter named as CZTS-ref). Subsequently, CdS covered crystals were implemented in the so-called monograin membranes. Membranes consist of thin layer of transparent, low shrinkage polymer into which microcrystals are semi-immersed in the middle of curing process. The front side of the crystals remain intact from the polymer and after complete polymerization, the membranes are covered with window layer. More details about preparation of the monograin layer solar cells were described in [6].

Figure 1. Scheme of combined 2-step process for heterojunction formation.

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3 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Electron Beam Induced Current (EBIC) measurements were
4 performed by using a Merlin, Carl Zeiss Microscopy, Germany. EBIC mapping was performed by
5 specimen current amplifier, model - Type 31, GW Electronics Ins., USA. The accelerating voltage of
6 20 kV for surface EBIC mapping and 10 kV for cross- section imaging was used in the SEM.
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10 The room temperature current-voltage characteristics of monograin layer solar cells were measured
11 with a Keithley 2400 source meter under standard test conditions (AM 1.5, 100 mW cm^{-2}) using a
12 Newport Oriel Class A 91195A solar simulator. The temperature-dependent measurements were
13 performed in the closed-cycle He cryostat by using halogen lamp. The position of the halogen lamp was
14 calibrated to match the current value measured standard test conditions. External Quantum Efficiency
15 (EQE) was measured using a computer-controlled SPM-2 prism monochromator. The generated
16 photocurrent was detected at 0 V bias voltage at room temperature by using a 250 W halogen lamp and
17 DSP lock-in amplifier.
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23 Compositional changes on the CZTS interface were analyzed by Kratos Analytical AXIS Ultra DLD
24 X-ray photoelectron spectrometer (XPS). In order to collect the signal of photoexcited electrons, the
25 CZTS powder mounted on rotational sample holder by ultra-high vacuum proof carbon tape was excited
26 by monochromatic Al $K\alpha$ X-ray source (1486.6 eV) at 15 kV and 150 W. Hybrid lens mode in
27 conjunction with aperture slot view (400 x 800 μm) and pass energies of 160 eV and 20 eV were set to
28 collect the survey and high-resolution photoelectron spectra, respectively.
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34 **3 Results and discussion.**

35 **3.1 XPS analysis**

36 Surface composition of CZTS powder after first CdS deposition process followed by air-annealing at
37 225 °C was investigated by XPS. Figure 2a shows the XPS survey spectrum of three different samples:
38 I- the surface of CZTS powder after removing the annealed CdS buffer layer (blue spectrum), II- the
39 surface of $\text{Cu}_2(\text{Zn}_{0.8}\text{Cd}_{0.2})\text{SnS}_4$ powder as a proof for Cd inclusion to the lattice (purple spectrum), and
40 III- fresh CdS on top of CZTS without annealing (orange spectrum). $\text{Cu}_2(\text{Zn}_{0.8}\text{Cd}_{0.2})\text{SnS}_4$ powder was
41 investigated also in the previous study [13] and Figure 2b shows the high-resolution spectrum of the Cd
42 3d core level, respectively. The peaks of Cd $3d_{3/2}$ and Cd $3d_{5/2}$, which are located at 412.2 and 405.4
43 eV, can be assigned to Cd^{2+} in CdS. The Cd 3d peaks at 411.7 and 404.9 eV correspond to Cd^{2+} in
44 $\text{Cu}_2(\text{Zn}_x\text{Cd}_{1-x})\text{SnS}_4$ solid solution. This gives us a solid proof that after CZTS/CdS air-annealing an
45 ultra-thin $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}_x\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{SnS}_4$ layer on CZTS crystals was formed. The signal of O 1s and C 1s in every
46 survey spectrum is due to atmospheric contamination.
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Figure 2. a) XPS survey spectrum of three different samples: I- the surface of CZTS powder after removing the annealed CdS buffer layer (blue spectrum), II- the surface of $\text{Cu}_2(\text{Zn}_{0.8}\text{Cd}_{0.2})\text{SnS}_4$ powder (purple spectrum), and III- fresh CdS on top of CZTS without annealing (orange spectrum) and b) corresponding Cd 3d core level spectra.

3.2 Device characterization

Room temperature I - V characteristics and EQE of a studied CZTS monograin layer solar cells are shown in the Figure 3a and 3b, respectively. The combined process for heterojunction formation improved slightly V_{OC} values from 723 mV to 735 mV, the main improvement was in the current density values (J_{SC}) from 20.5 to 23.6 mA/cm^2 , and in fill factor (FF) from 59.4 to 67.7%. Serial resistance of the monograin layer solar cells based on CZTS-modified absorber was significantly reduced from 2.4 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ to 0.67 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$. As a result, the enhanced device performance with power conversion efficiency 11.7% was obtained. PCE is calculated by using image analysis tool for active surface area (yellow area $\sim 75\%$ from total contact area), which is estimated from EBIC top view image (Figure 4a).

Figure 3 a) I - V characteristics and b) EQE spectra of CZTS monograin layer solar cells based on heterojunction prepared by single step (CZTS-ref) and two-step process (CZTS-modified).

EBIC allows to image the collection efficiency of charge carriers in device. In EBIC, the electron beam illuminates a nanometer-scale region in the semiconductor specimen and generates electron-hole pairs. A portion of them are collected at the device contacts, giving rise to a photocurrent. By scanning the electron beam, a two-dimensional map of collected photocurrent in the device is constructed [16].

Figure 4b shows higher magnification EBIC top view of monograin layer solar cell. The dark areas are non-conductive polymer, where charge-carriers are not generated and light areas show working crystals, where photocurrent is produced. EBIC cross-section image in Figure 4c is shown as split picture of secondary electron and photocurrent images obtained simultaneously, showing on one side the SEM and on the other side the EBIC image.

Figure 4. Photocurrent image of a) full device with size $3.1 \times 3.1 \text{ mm}^2$, b) SEM and EBIC image from top-view of the same area of device and c) SEM and EBIC image from cross-section of the same area of device.

EQE spectrum was used to study the spectral response of the CZTS monograin layer solar cells. Figure 3b shows the normalized EQE spectra of monograin layer solar cells based on CZTS-ref and CZTS-modified heterojunction. The absorption edge shifts to longer wavelengths with addition of Cd into CZTS surface layer. The effective band gap energy (E_g^*) of absorber material was evaluated from the linear segment of the low-energy side of the construction $(\text{EQE} \cdot E)^2$ vs. E curves. Decrease of E_g^* from 1.566 eV to 1.548 eV by formation of ultra-thin $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}_x\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{SnS}_4$ layer on CZTS crystals was confirmed.

To understand in more detail the electrical behavior of highest efficiency CZTS monograin layer solar cell, the temperature dependent current–voltage characteristics were analyzed.

3.3 Temperature dependence of I - V characteristics.

The dark and illuminated I - V curves measured at different temperatures are presented in Figure 5a and 5b. The solar cell parameters obtained from direct measurements are presented in Figure 6a and 6b. The maximum efficiency was achieved at $T = 270 \text{ K}$ mostly due to higher FF and V_{OC} . Calculated efficiencies are not calibrated because we used halogen light source. The distance between the lamp and the device was set to match the short circuit current density value from RT I - V measurements under

the solar simulator. All solar cell parameters gained from the fittings of temperature dependence measurements are corresponding to total area of the device.

Figure 5. Temperature dependence of a) dark and b) illuminated I - V curves.

The temperature dependence of V_{OC} is often used to determine the dominating recombination processes in solar cells. It is known, that at temperatures close to room temperature the $V_{OC}(T)$ curve shows a linear part and the extrapolation of this line to 0 K results in the activation energy Φ [17–19]. In the case of $\Phi < E_g$, the dominating recombination is related to the interface recombination. However, in our case, $V_{OC}(T)$ curve shows only a limited number of points in the $V_{OC}(T)$ curve, which show a linear trend. This is an indication, that the activation energy $\Phi \approx 1.3$ eV is probably not completely correct.

Figure 6. Temperature dependence of a) open circuit voltage and efficiency, b) current density and fill factor.

In order to get additional information about solar cell properties we performed a fitting of all I - V curves. Dark curves were fitted using a double diode model:

$$J = J_{01} \left\{ \exp \left[\frac{q(V+JR_S)}{n_1 kT} \right] - 1 \right\} + J_{02} \left\{ \exp \left[\frac{q(V+JR_S)}{n_2 kT} \right] - 1 \right\} + \frac{V+JR_S}{R_{SH}} \quad (1)$$

and illuminated curves were fitted using a single diode model:

$$J = J_0 \left\{ \exp \left[\frac{q(V+JR_S)}{nkT} \right] - 1 \right\} + \frac{V+JR_S}{R_{SH}} - J_L \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } J_0 = J_{00} \exp \left(\frac{-\Phi_B}{nkT} \right) \quad (3)$$

is the saturation and J_L the photogenerated current densities. The expression kT is the thermal energy where k is the Boltzmann constant and T the absolute temperature. The diode ideality factor n , the series resistance R_S and parallel shunt resistance R_{SH} account for non-ideal behavior of the solar cell. Here J_{00} is an only weekly temperature dependent pre-factor, Φ_B is the activation energy of the saturation current. All the fittings were done using an algorithm proposed in [20] and ideality factors were not fixed during the fittings. An example of this fitting for $T = 300$ K and $T = 120$ K is given in Figures 7a-d.

Figure 7. I-V curve fitting results with Eq. 1 and 2 at $T = 300$ K (a- dark, c- light) and $T = 120$ K (b- dark, d- light). R_{SH} related losses are shown as dotted line and diode curves as blue and magenta lines.

Dark curves in Figure 7a, b show typical for non-ideal solar cell double diode behavior, where the first diode has so-called “normal” behavior and the second diode has very high value of ideality factor at different temperatures related to different recombination processes. At room temperature n_1 and n_2 have values 1.62 and 3.7, respectively. Such high value of the ideality factor for the second diode represents

a tunneling component, which has a similar exponential dependence as a diode. It is often called as a “weak” diode [21]. Therefore we do not present parameters for this diode and show only results for the first “normal” diode.

Result of light curves fitting in Figures 7c, d shows that our cell has quite big current loss due to parallel shunt resistance R_{SH} at lower temperature ($T = 120$ K) while at room temperature due to relatively high value of R_{SH} only diode current can be used in the fitting. At higher voltages, the role of series resistance R_S is also seen. Both resistances have a certain temperature dependence, see Figure 8a, b.

Figure 8. Temperature dependence of a) R_S and b) R_{SH} . Fitting results of R_S with Eq. 4 are shown as solid lines.

R_S shows a simple exponential dependence for both light and dark:

$$R_S(T) = R_{S0}/(1 + \beta \exp(-E_a/kT)) \quad (4)$$

with activation energies $E_a = 59$ meV and $E_a = 99$ meV for light and dark curves, respectively. In most cases this activation energy is assigned to the back contact barrier height. The difference between activation energies for dark and light cases is an indication of a small photoconductivity. More complicated behavior can be observed for R_{SH} in dark and light, see Figure 8b. At higher temperatures, R_{SH}^{light} of light curves is increasing almost linearly with temperature and therefore the current loss due to R_{SH}^{light} is smaller at higher temperatures. This ohmic behavior of R_{SH}^{light} can be related to ohmic shunts due to pinholes in the polymer layer between crystals or via low-resistance grain boundaries, because some monograins are formed from separate crystal blocks. At low temperatures, the R_{SH}^{light} is increasing again, but this exponential increase has a different origin related to thermal activation of the semiconductor layer. It has an activation energy $E_a = 19.9 \pm 0.5$ meV. We assume that this rather small activation energy is related to some shallow trap level in the CdS buffer layer. However, the R_{SH}^{dark} values obtained from dark curves are almost 1000 times higher than values obtained for light curves. While the decrease of R_{SH}^{light} with illumination is observed also in thin film solar cells [22], but in our case the decrease is larger than expected. This means that the shunting current density is strongly

influenced by the illumination and is probably related to the photoconductivity of buffer layer. CdS layer is around the crystals when the grains are embedded into polymer layer. In the back contact formation process, it will be removed from back side by etching and mechanical polishing, but low probability remains that CdS layer can be in touch with back contact.

The temperature dependence of the diode ideality factor n usually gives valuable information about possible recombination mechanisms in solar cells [23]. In case of tunneling assisted interface recombination, it was shown that the temperature dependence of ideality factor is given by [24]:

$$n = \frac{E_{00}}{\alpha kT} \coth\left(\frac{E_{00}}{kT}\right), \quad (5)$$

where the characteristic tunneling energy E_{00} is a function of the net acceptor concentration N_A :

$$E_{00} = (q\hbar/2)[N_A/(m^*\varepsilon)]^{0.5}, \quad (6)$$

where, \hbar - Planck constant, q - the elementary charge, ε - the semiconductor's dielectric constant, and m^* - the effective tunneling mass, and

$$\alpha = \frac{\omega_p/\varepsilon_p}{\omega_p/\varepsilon_p + \omega_n/\varepsilon_n}, \quad (7)$$

where ω_p , ω_n and ε_p , ε_n are the space charge region widths and dielectric constants of the absorber and the buffer, respectively.

The temperature dependence of n and the fitting result with Eq. 5 are given in Figure 9.

Figure 9. The diode ideality factors n as a function of temperature and fitted curves for tunneling-enhanced interface recombination model (Eq. 5).

According to fitting result, the dominant recombination in our solar cell is indeed related to tunneling-enhanced interface recombination with the tunneling energy $E_{00} = 68$ meV. The same model is true also for dark curves, where the tunneling energy is $E_{00} = 29$ meV, however the parameter α has a value of 0.868. This means that part of the space charge region extends into buffer layer, see Eq. (7). The tunneling energy for light curves is slightly higher than the tunneling energy measured in thin film

CZTSSe cells ($E_{00} = 41.5$ meV) [25] and is an indication that the carrier concentration in our CZTS is quite high, see Eq. (6). Therefore, the series resistance R_s of our cell is also fairly low, i.e. around $0.7 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ at room temperature.

More information can be obtained by examining the temperature dependence of saturation current density J_0 . From the Eq. (2) for the J_0 , the following expression can be derived:

$$\ln\left(\frac{J_0}{J_{00}}\right) = \frac{-\Phi_B}{nkT} \quad (8)$$

By reorganizing Eq. (6), we obtain

$$n \ln(J_0) = n \ln(J_{00}) - \frac{\Phi_B}{kT} \quad (9)$$

A plot of $n \ln(J_0)$ versus $1/kT$ should yield a straight line with a slope corresponding to the activation energy of the saturation current Φ_B , see Figure 10.

Figure 10. $n \ln(J_0)$ vs $1000/T$ plot and the fitting result with Eq. 9.

Obtained activation energy values of the saturation current are lower than the estimated CZTS room temperature band gap energy $E_g = 1.548$ eV. It is known that values $\Phi_B < E_g$ would indicate interface recombination as the dominant mechanism due to Fermi-level pinning or band gap narrowing at the interface. It is interesting that the temperature dependence of V_{OC} provided lower activation energy: $\Phi = 1.3$ eV, see Figure 6a. It is known, that as soon as tunneling becomes important, the ideality factor n becomes temperature dependent inducing non-linear terms into V_{OC} vs T dependence and therefore, even for relatively high temperatures the temperature dependence of V_{OC} may give not accurate activation energy.

4 Conclusions

The influence of the Cd diffusion into surface of CZTS and replacement of Cu doped CdS by fresh CdS buffer layer on the electrical behavior of highest efficiency CZTS monograin layer solar cell by temperature dependent $I-V$ characteristics was analyzed. XPS surface analysis showed that after

CZTS/CdS air-annealing an ultra-thin $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}_x\text{Cd}_{1-x}\text{SnS}_4$ layer on CZTS crystals was formed. After replacing the annealed CdS: Cu by fresh CdS buffer layer, the device efficiency of 11.7% was achieved. The V_{oc} value improved slightly from 723 mV to 735 mV, but the main improvement was in the current density value from 20.5 to 23.6 mA/cm², and in fill factor from 59.4 to 67.7%. Serial resistance was significantly reduced from 2.4 Ω cm² to 0.67 Ω cm². To understand in more detail the electrical behavior of highest efficiency CZTS monograin layer solar cell, the temperature dependent current–voltage characteristics were analyzed. According to fitting result, the dominant recombination in our solar cell is related to tunneling-enhanced interface recombination with the tunneling energy $E_{00} = 68$ meV. Analysis of the temperature dependence of the R_{SH} indicated to two types of shunts in our device, which remains a future challenge.

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